

Enhancement of $0.65\text{Pb}(\text{Mg}_{1/3}\text{Nb}_{2/3})\text{O}_3-0.35\text{PbTiO}_3$ thick films: Effects of flash lamp annealing

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Abstract

The deposition of high-quality piezoceramic thick films is challenging on temperature-sensitive substrates. Powder aerosol deposition is a promising room-temperature technique for fabricating dense piezoceramic thick films; however, annealing is still required to improve their functional properties. As an alternative to conventional furnaces, not suited for metallic or polymeric substrates, flash lamp annealing enables selective annealing of the films without damaging the substrates. In this work, 3 μm -thick $0.65\text{Pb}(\text{Mg}_{1/3}\text{Nb}_{2/3})\text{O}_3\text{-}0.35\text{PbTiO}_3$ thick films are prepared by powder aerosol deposition on 0.8 mm-thick stainless steel substrates and are flash-lamp annealed afterwards. The annealed films exhibit an increased permittivity of 580 and remanent polarization of $31 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$, comparable to results obtained by conventional annealing at $500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The enhanced ferroelectric properties are linked a release of the strain in the films. This work demonstrates the possibility to deposit and anneal piezoelectric thick films on temperature sensitive substrates.

Keywords

Flash lamp annealing, PMN-PT, Ferroelectric thick films, Powder aerosol deposition

1 Introduction

Electronics applications, in particular wearable sensors and the Internet of Things (IoT), rely on piezoelectric materials for sensing, actuation, and energy harvesting. They require improved solutions for energy storage and electromechanical conversion. Promising candidates are relaxor-ferroelectrics with high dielectric permittivity and polarization. They also exhibit strong charge–discharge capability under large currents, making them suitable for thick- and thin-film-based power-conditioning electronics and compact pulsed-power energy storage devices. With a morphotropic phase boundary composition, $0.65\text{Pb}(\text{Mg}_{1/3}\text{Nb}_{2/3})\text{O}_3\text{--}0.35\text{PbTiO}_3$ (PMN–35PT) bulk ceramics demonstrates excellent dielectric, piezoelectric, and ferroelectric properties, exhibiting d_{33} of 700 pC N^{-1} [1–3].

Recently, powder aerosol deposition, a room temperature spray-coating method, has been shown as an effective method to grow ceramic thick films on temperature sensitive substrates, such as polymers and metals [4–6]. Powder aerosol deposition relies on the collision of high-speed particles with the substrate, leading to densification through high kinetic energy [5, 7, 8]. This process creates films with internal compressive stress and grains with limited size, in the order of a few tens of nanometers. As these characteristics are hindering ferroelectric properties in thick films, moderate thermal annealing is necessary to improve the functional properties [9].

It was shown in literature that annealing powder aerosol deposited PMN-35PT thick films on stainless steel substrates at $500\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 hour significantly improves the ferroelectric response by relaxing internal stresses [9, 10]. While stainless steel can withstand an annealing temperature of $500\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, this is not the case for most polymeric and glass substrates. To circumvent this limitation, selective annealing of the film can be performed via flash lamp annealing (FLA), maintaining the substrate at a relatively low temperature. This method has recently been demonstrated to crystallize lead titanate zirconate thin films on various temperature sensitive glass substrates as well as on thin, flexible glass [11, 12]. FLA is based on the absorption of sub-millisecond light pulses of strong intensity and broad spectrum. Depending on the material absorptivity, selective annealing take place [13]. An ultrafast annealing technique, FLA allows to anneal in a few seconds areas up to hundreds of square centimeters in ambient atmosphere.

In this work, we study the use of flash lamp annealing as a method to improve the ferroelectric properties of powder aerosol deposited $3\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ -thick $0.65\text{Pb}(\text{Mg}_{1/3}\text{Nb}_{2/3})\text{O}_3\text{--}0.35\text{PbTiO}_3$ thick films on 0.8 mm -thick stainless steel substrates. Through finite element modeling, we show the

feasibility that annealing temperatures of 500 °C can be reached across the PMN-35PT thick film. Then, we optimize the annealing parameters experimentally, demonstrating improved dielectric and ferroelectric properties compared to the as-deposited films. We demonstrate that the increased ferroelectric response is due to the release of strain generated by powder aerosol deposition in the PMN-35PT thick films.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Powders preparation

A $0.65\text{Pb}(\text{Mg}_{1/3}\text{Nb}_{2/3})\text{O}_3\text{-}0.35\text{PbTiO}_3$ (PMN-35PT) ceramic powder was synthesized using a mechanochemical approach with PbO (99.9 %, Sigma-Aldrich), MgO (99.95 %, Alfa Aesar), Nb_2O_5 (99.9 %, Sigma-Aldrich) and TiO_2 (99.8 %, Alfa Aesar) as starting reagents. $\text{Pb}(\text{Mg}_{1/3}\text{Nb}_{2/3})\text{O}_3$ and PbTiO_3 powders were synthesized separately, then mixed in a stoichiometric ratio and homogenized for 2 hours in a planetary mill (PM 400, Retsch, Germany). Homogenization was carried out at 200 rpm, in the presence of isopropanol, using yttria-stabilized zirconia (YSZ) balls with diameter of 3 mm. The mixture was then mechanochemically activated for 24 hours, using the same planetary mill. This step was carried out at 300 rpm using tungsten carbide milling balls with a diameter of 20 mm. Afterwards, the powder was milled again for 2 hours in the presence of isopropanol, using YSZ balls at 200 rpm before being heated in a furnace at 900 °C for 1 hour, with heating and cooling rates of 5 K min⁻¹. Finally, the powder was milled for another 30 min in the presence of isopropanol, using YSZ balls at 200 rpm. Details of the powder preparation have been previously described in [10].

2.2 Powder aerosol deposition

Prior to deposition, the PMN-35PT powder was sieved through an 80 µm mesh and vacuum dried for 12 hours at 100 °C. The powder was deposited onto AISI 304 stainless steel substrates with a polished surface. The substrates dimensions were 15 mm × 15 mm × 0.8 mm. Powder aerosol deposition was performed using equipment provided by InVerTec, Germany. N₂ was used as a carrier gas with a gas flow rate of 4 L min⁻¹ and a pressure of 2 mbar in the deposition chamber. The nozzle, with a geometry of 0.5 × 10 mm², was kept at a distance of 5 mm from

the substrate. After deposition, the films were cleaned with isopropanol.

2.3 Flash lamp annealing

Crystalline films were annealed using a PulseForge Invent flash lamp annealer (NovaCentrix, Austin, TX, USA) equipped with a Xe lamp. The annealing conditions are determined by the number of pulses, the repetition rate, the pulse duration, and the energy density per pulse. The power density per pulse is influenced by the last two parameters. The energy density was calibrated using a bolometer.

2.4 Electrical characterization

100 nm-thick Pt circular electrodes, with a diameter of 500 μm , were deposited on the top surface of the thin films by sputtering. The electrodes were patterned using a shadow mask.

Electrical characterization was performed on a TF Analyzer 2000 (aixACCT Systems, Aachen, Germany). Relative permittivity and dielectric loss were measured with a probing AC signal of 100 V at 1 kHz as a function of the DC voltage. Polarization versus electrical field hysteresis were measured with a sinusoidal waveform at 100 Hz.

2.5 Microstructural characterization

Standard θ - 2θ X-ray diffraction (XRD) was performed to study the phase composition and orientation of the films using a MiniFlex 600-C diffractometer (Rigaku, Tokyo, Japan) with Cu-K α radiation. The patterns were recorded in the 10° – 90° 2θ range with a step size of 0.005° and a scan speed of 5 s per step.

XRD ψ scans were performed to study the strain in the films using a D8 Discover diffractometer (Bruker, Billerica, MA, USA) with Cu-K α radiation. The patterns were recorded for ψ values of 0° to 75° in the 30.00° – 32.50° 2θ range with a step size of 0.04° and a scan speed of 90 s per step.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Flash lamp annealing temperature modeling

Annealing temperature is a key parameter for improving the ferroelectric properties of PMN-PT films grown by powder aerosol deposition [14]. The brevity of the flash lamp annealing process, while an advantage to reduce processing time and to avoid overheating substrates, can prove inconvenient to measure the in-situ temperature. Finite element modeling is a useful approach to estimate the temperature during the annealing process.

Flash lamp annealing is controlled by four main parameters: number of pulses, pulse duration, repetition rate and energy density. The pulse duration and energy density together determine the power density, according to Eq. 1:

$$P = \frac{E}{t}, \quad (1)$$

where P is the power density, E is the energy density and t is the duration. Modeling the impact of these four parameters on the annealing temperature allows to quickly optimize the flash lamp annealing process.

A 3 μm -thick PMN-35PT film on a 0.8 mm-thick stainless steel 304 substrate was modeled using the SimPulse software in surface mode. The software model accounts for the thickness and intrinsic properties of both the substrate and the PMN-35PT film. The surface mode includes into the calculations the absorbance of the sample in its entirety. Due to the opacity of both the film and the substrate, the absorption of the sample was approximated to 100 %. The results of the modeled maximum temperature per pulse at the PMN-35PT surface and at the interface between PMN-35PT and the stainless steel substrate are shown in Fig. 1.

The effect of 50 to 500 pulses on the annealing temperature was modeled and the results are presented in Fig. 1 a and b for the PMN-35PT surface and the interface between PMN-35PT and the stainless steel, respectively. The temperature at the PMN-35PT surface reaches between 300 °C and 340 °C. At the interface between PMN-35PT and the stainless steel, the temperature spans from 200 °C to 250 °C.

Figure 1: Finite element modeling. Maximum temperature per pulse profiles at the PMN-35PT top surface (a, c, e and g) and at the PMN-35PT/steel interface (b, d, f and h) as a function of the number of pulses, the energy density, the pulse duration and the repetition rate, respectively. The values of the fixed parameters for each subfigure are given in the main text. To enhance the visual distinction between the data series in (a) and (b), markers have been added on the last data point of each data series. Note the different scales between each row.

According to literature, PMN-PT films grown by powder aerosol deposition must be annealed at 500 °C to improve their recoverable energy density [14]. With the FLA parameters selected for the modeling, it appears clearly that, even with 500 pulses applied to the PMN-35PT film, the temperature saturates more than 150 °C below the required annealing temperature. It is necessary to vary other FLA parameters to reach 500 °C if the number of pulses cannot allow to reach the PMN-35PT film. Increasing the number of pulses beyond saturation temperature is not beneficial. With each FLA pulse, the sample undergoes successive heating-cooling cycles which generates strain in the sample [11, 12]. The optimum number of pulses was determined to be at the onset of saturation, at 100 pulses.

To reach temperatures above 500 °C in the PMN-35PT film, the effect of the energy density per pulse has been modeled for values from 1 J cm⁻² to 4 J cm⁻². The results of the modeling at the PMN-35PT surface and at the interface between PMN-35PT and the stainless steel are presented in Fig. 1 c and d, respectively. At the PMN-35PT surface, the temperature ranges from 330 °C to 1100 °C. Temperatures between 240 °C and 770 °C are reached at the interface between PMN-35PT and stainless steel.

To anneal the PMN-35PT film at 500 °C [14], the entirety of the film must be brought above 500 °C. While this temperature is achieved at 2 J cm⁻² and higher energy density for the PMN-35PT, at least 3 J cm⁻² are necessary for the back of the film, located at the interface between PMN-35PT and stainless steel. This is due to the thermal gradient created by FLA through the film thickness [15]. From these results, the optimum energy density was determined to be 3 J cm⁻².

The impact of the pulse duration on the annealing temperature was modeled as it is closely related to the energy density through the power density. Its effect was modeled for pulses of 100 μs to 350 μs. The results for the PMN-35PT surface and the interface between PMN-35PT and stainless steel are presented in Fig. 1 e and f, respectively. At the end of the pulses, after 50 s, the temperature appears to have reached saturation for all modeled pulse durations. The temperature at the PMN-35PT surface reaches between 1640 °C and 800 °C. At the interface between PMN-35PT and the stainless steel, the model indicates temperatures between 750 °C and 600 °C.

Due to the energy density per pulse delivered to the film being kept constant at 3 J cm⁻², it is coherent for the higher temperatures being reached for the shorter pulse durations. It should

be noted that shorter pulses lead to larger temperature gradient across the PMN-35PT film thickness with between 890 °C and 210 °C of difference between the top and bottom surfaces of the film. To obtain a more homogeneous annealing across the PMN-35PT film thickness, longer pulses of 300 μ s or 350 μ s must be selected. To ensure some margin to tune the FLA repetition rate, it was decided not to work with pulses of 350 μ s as they lead to a temperature as low as 600 °C at the interface between PMN-35PT and the stainless steel, very close to the minimum required annealing temperature of 500 °C [14].

The effect of a repetition rate from 1 Hz to 3 Hz on the annealing temperature was then modeled. Fig. 1 g and h show the results for the PMN-35PT surface and the interface between PMN-35PT and stainless steel, respectively. Temperatures from 650 °C to 960 °C are reached at the PMN-35PT surface. At the interface between PMN-35PT and the stainless steel, the temperature is between 400 °C and 710 °C. At 1 Hz, the PMN-35PT film is not heated up sufficiently to reach the minimum annealing temperature of 500 °C [14] through the whole thickness. At 3 Hz, the temperature reaches a significantly higher temperature but the rapid succession of heating–cooling cycles for each FLA pulse can lead to significant damage within the film and substrate [12]. A repetition rate of 2 Hz is appropriate to anneal the PMN-35PT films.

The modeled temperatures 10 μ m below the interface and at the stainless steel lower surface are presented in Supplementary Fig. S1. The temperature drops significantly through the stainless steel thickness, the lower surface remaining below 500 °C.

From the modeling results, the optimal parameters to anneal a 3 μ m-thick PMN-35PT film on a 0.8 mm-thick stainless steel 304 substrate are 100 pulses of 3 J cm⁻² and 300 μ s with a repetition rate of 2 Hz.

3.2 Optimization of ferroelectric characteristics

Several 3 μ m-thick PMN-35PT films were deposited on 0.8 mm-thick stainless steel 304 substrates. Their characteristic values as ferroelectrics were then compared. The investigated parameters are the permittivity, ϵ , and dielectric loss at 0 V, as well as the remanent polarization, P_r , and maximum polarization, P_{\max} . To ensure comparability, all films were deposited from the same powder batch, with four substrates processed simultaneously. The flash lamp annealing process of the PMN-35PT films was optimized by tuning the number of pulses, pulse duration,

energy density, and repetition rate. In the following paragraph we show that it is essential to identify processing conditions that achieve an optimal balance between enhancement of the functional properties and degradation of the films. The results are presented in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Dielectric and ferroelectric characteristic values of 3 μm -thick PMN-35PT films on stainless steel as a function of their FLA parameters. Samples were annealed with a varying (a) number of pulses, (b) pulse duration and (c) repetition rate. Permittivity and dielectric losses were measured at 1 kHz while polarization versus electrical field hysteresis loops were measured at 100 Hz with a sinusoidal signal. The dashed line indicates the maximum polarization measured powder in aerosol deposited PMN-35PT films annealed at 500 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ by conventional annealing. The data points for 0 pulses, 0 μs and 0 Hz correspond to the reference sample which was not annealed.

To evaluate the effect of the number of pulses, samples were annealed with either 200 pulses or 500 pulses. In both cases, the pulse duration was 300 μs , the energy density was 1 J cm^{-2} and the repetition rate was 2 Hz. As shown in Fig. 2 a, the dielectric permittivity increases from 190 for the reference sample to 220 and 300 after 200 and 500 pulses, respectively. Dielectric losses are 2.3 % and 3.4 %, respectively, compared to 3.5 % for the reference sample. After 200 pulses, the remanent polarization, P_r , and the maximum polarization, P_{max} , are 14 $\mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$

and $35 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$, respectively. After 500 pulses, these values are $49 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$ and $56 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$. For comparison, the reference sample displays a remanent polarization of $7 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$ and a maximum polarization of $27 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$.

The sample annealed with 500 pulses presents increased dielectric losses by a factor of 1.5 compared to the sample annealed with 200 pulses. Its maximum polarization is higher than the value of $54 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$ that was measured for PMN-35PT conventionally annealed at $500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. These results indicate a degradation of the film quality which could be attributed to excessive heating-cooling cycles generating strain in the sample [12]. It is consistent with the modeling results presented in the previous section.

The sample annealed with 200 pulses demonstrates reduced dielectric losses and improved permittivity, remanent polarization and maximum polarization as compared to the reference sample. Contrary to the sample annealed with 500 pulses, these results imply an improvement of the PMN-35PT film quality after annealing by FLA.

As described in the previous section, the pulses power density is dependent on both the pulses duration and energy density, following Eq. 1. Samples have been annealed with a pulse duration of $250 \mu\text{s}$ and $300 \mu\text{s}$ and the results are displayed in Fig. 2 b. For both samples, 100 pulses were applied with an energy density of 3 J cm^{-2} and a repetition rate of 2 Hz . The permittivity and dielectric losses are 490 and 4.7 % for $250 \mu\text{s}$ pulses; and 560 and 5.1 % for $300 \mu\text{s}$ pulses, respectively. The remanent polarization is $27 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$ and $31 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$ for the $250 \mu\text{s}$ pulses sample and $300 \mu\text{s}$ pulses sample, respectively. The corresponding maximum polarization is $58 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$ and $65 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$, respectively.

Concerning the pulse duration, there is a trend of improvement of the permittivity, remanent polarization and maximum polarization with longer pulse duration. This trend is accompanied with a trend of increasing dielectric losses with increasing pulse duration. Similarly to the results previously obtained with 500 pulses at 1 J cm^{-2} , the maximum polarization exceeds the value for PMN-35PT films conventionally annealed at $500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, for the samples with both $250 \mu\text{s}$ and $300 \mu\text{s}$ pulses. These results indicate that pulses shorter than $250 \mu\text{s}$ would be beneficial to the PMN-35PT films as longer pulses lead to film degradation.

To determine if larger energy density during annealing is beneficial to the PMN-35PT films, a sample was annealed at 4 J cm^{-2} with pulses of $400 \mu\text{s}$. These parameters allow to maintain the same power density of 1 W m^{-2} as for the sample annealed at 3 J cm^{-2} with pulses of

300 μs . The number of pulses and the repetition rate were kept constant at 100 pulses and 2 Hz. The permittivity, dielectric losses, remanent polarization and maximum polarization are 1120, 11.9 %, 16 $\mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$ and 92 $\mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$, respectively.

At equivalent power density, the dielectric losses are increased by a factor of 2.3 for an energy density of 4 J cm^{-2} as compared to 3 J cm^{-2} . The increased maximum polarization, reaching values 1.7 times larger than for the PMN-35PT film conventionally annealed at 500 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, can be attributed to leakage due to the film degradation. The experimental results confirm the modeling results, indicating that the optimum energy density to anneal 3 μm -thick PMN-35PT films by FLA is 3 J cm^{-2} .

Finally, the effect of the FLA repetition rate on the PMN-35PT films was analyzed, as shown in Fig. 2 c. To limit the damage to the PMN-35PT films through fast successive heating-cooling cycles [12], only repetition rates of 1 Hz and 2 Hz have been studied. For these samples, 100 pulses were applied with a pulse duration of 300 μs and an energy density of 3 J cm^{-2} . The sample annealed with a repetition rate of 1 Hz has a permittivity of 330 and dielectric losses of 4.0 %. The sample annealed at 2 Hz has a permittivity and dielectric losses of 560 and 5.1 %, respectively. The remanent polarization and maximum polarization of the sample annealed at 1 Hz are 17 $\mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$ and 45 $\mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$, respectively and they are 31 $\mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$ and 65 $\mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$, respectively, for the sample annealed at 2 Hz.

As for the effect of the pulses duration, the permittivity, remanent polarization and maximum polarization improve with higher repetition rate while the dielectric losses increase. A repetition rate of 2 Hz seems to lead to some degradation of the PMN-35PT film as the maximum polarization is larger than that of the film conventionally annealed at 500 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, indicating leakage.

The complexity of the flash lamp annealing process requires to compromise between avoiding damaging the PMN-35PT film and reaching temperatures sufficient to anneal it. The experimental results indicate that good parameters to anneal a 3 μm -thick PMN-35PT film on a stainless steel substrate are 100 pulses with a pulse duration of 300 μs , an energy density of 3 J cm^{-2} and a repetition rate of 2 Hz.

3.3 Flash lamp annealing comparison to conventional annealing

To compare the effect on powder aerosol deposited PMN-35PT thick films of flash lamp annealing and of conventional annealing at 500 °C for 1 hour, permittivity and dielectric loss have been measured, as well as polarization versus electrical field hysteresis loops (P - E loops). For reference, the properties of an as-deposited PMN-35PT film were also measured. The results are presented in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Comparison of the annealing technique on the dielectric and ferroelectric properties of PMN-35PT for as-deposited, flash lamp annealed and conventionally annealed thick films. (a) Permittivity and (b) dielectric loss at 1 kHz. (c) Polarization and (d) current density versus electrical field with a sinusoidal waveform at 100 Hz.

Flash lamp annealing significantly increases the permittivity of the PMN-35PT thick films from 180 to 580. The dielectric loss remains similar, ranging from 2.9 % to 5.1 %. The conventionally annealed PMN-35PT sample reaches a permittivity of 770 with the dielectric loss increasing to 7.8 %.

With a coercive field, E_c , of 273 $\text{kV}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$, a remanent polarization P_r , of 7 $\mu\text{C}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ and a maximum polarization, P_{max} , of 28 $\mu\text{C}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$, as-deposited PMN-35PT films do not display

pronounced ferroelectric switching.

Both flash lamp annealing and conventional annealing enable clear ferroelectric switching in the PMN-35PT films. The flash lamp annealed film has E_c , P_r and P_{max} values of 273 kV cm⁻¹, 31 μC cm⁻² and 65 μC cm⁻², respectively. It should be noted that the P - E loop is rounded, indicative of leakage, contrary to the conventionally annealed PMN-35PT film which shows a significantly narrower P - E loop. For the latter, E_c , P_r and P_{max} values are 87 kV cm⁻¹, 18 μC cm⁻² and 54 μC cm⁻², respectively. The values obtained in this work for the conventionally annealed film are consistent with those reported in literature for PMN-35PT [10].

Ferroelectric switching can be induced in the films by a short FLA treatment compared to hours in the furnace.

3.4 Strain release through flash lamp annealing

The effect of flash lamp annealing on both micro- and macrostrain in PMN-35PT thick films was analyzed by XRD through θ - 2θ and ψ scans.

The θ - 2θ scans for the as-deposited and flash lamp annealed PMN-35PT films in Fig. 4 a) indicate a polycrystalline structure, as expected from powder aerosol deposited films. As no clear differences are noticeable between the scans, Rietveld refinement was performed to calculate the crystallite sizes and the microstrain. The results of the refinements are presented in Supplementary Fig. S2.

Figure 4: XRD analysis of microstrain in for as-deposited, flash lamp annealed and conventionally annealed PMN-35PT films. (a) θ - 2θ scans and (b) the crystallite sizes and the microstrain. The PMN-35PT reflections are indexed with the PDF Card n° 04-016-2582 [16].

The crystallite size in Fig. 4 b) is 14.08 nm for the as-deposited, 14.19 nm for the flash lamp

annealed and 16.09 nm for the conventionally annealed PMN-35PT films. For the conventionally annealed sample, crystallite size increased by 14 % compared to the as-deposited sample. While literature reports that annealing at 500 °C has a minor influence on PMN-35PT crystallite size [9], this 14 % increase in conventionally annealed films is significantly larger than the 1 % increase for the flash lamp annealed films. This could explain the difference in dielectric and ferroelectric properties of the flash lamp annealed films compared to the conventionally annealed films.

The microstrain got decreased by 24.7 % and 20.3 % by flash lamp and conventional annealing, respectively, as compared to the as-deposited film. These results are similar to those observed in literature [9].

In Fig. 5 a) the 2θ values for the (110) reflection of as-deposited PMN-35PT increase from 31.32° for $\psi = 0^\circ$ to 41.45° for $\psi = 75^\circ$. The flash lamp annealed film, in Fig. 5 b), shows almost constant 2θ values, with 31.41° for $\psi = 0^\circ$ and 31.42° for $\psi = 75^\circ$. The corresponding interplanar distances d_{110} are given in Fig. 4 c). For the as-deposited PM-35PT, the slope is -1.2906 pm with an intercept of 285.33 pm ($R^2 = 0.983$) while for the flash lamp annealed film, the slope is -0.0954 pm and the intercept of 284.49 pm ($R^2 = 0.298$). Considering a Poisson's ratio of 0.34 [17], the ϵ_{11} and the ϵ_{33} are -0.223 % and 0.230 % for the as-deposited film, respectively, and are -0.017 % and 0.017 % for flash lamp annealed PMN-35PT, respectively. This decrease of the macrostrain for the flash lamp annealed film as compared to the as-deposited film is consistent with the results obtained for the microstrain and with literature [9]. As suggested in literature, this strain release is likely the cause for the improved ferroelectric response described in the previous section [9, 18].

Figure 5: XRD analysis of macrostrain in for as-deposited and flash lamp annealed PMN-35PT thick films. ψ scans of PMN-35PT (110) reflection for (a) as-deposited and (b) flash lamp annealed thick films (c) macrostrain.

4 Conclusions and outlooks

In this work, we deposited 3 μm -thick $0.65\text{Pb}(\text{Mg}_{1/3}\text{Nb}_{2/3})\text{O}_3 - 0.35\text{PbTiO}_3$ thick films on 0.8 mm-thick stainless steel substrates via powder aerosol deposition and annealed them using flash lamp annealing. With finite element modeling, and through experimental optimization, we showed that 100 pulses FLA of 3 J cm^{-2} and $300 \mu\text{s}$ with a repetition rate of 2 Hz allow to reach a temperature of $500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ across the film.

After FLA, the PMN-35PT thick films exhibit an increased permittivity of 580 and reasonable dielectric loss of 5.1 %. They have a remanent polarization of $31 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$, compared to

7 $\mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$ for as-deposited samples and 18 $\mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$ for films conventionally annealed at 500 °C. This improved ferroelectric response is accompanied by a release of the strain in the PMN-35PT films.

The results are promising for the annealing of PMN-35PT thick films on temperature sensitive polymeric flexible substrates, for which conventional annealing is not possible. The method demonstrated in this work could also be applied to a wide range of ceramic material deposited by powder aerosol, enabling an efficient low temperature process for piezoelectric ceramics.

Data availability

The data that supports the findings of the study are included in the main text and the Supplementary Information. The raw data generated in this study have been deposited in the Zenodo repository under DOI (*will be updated after the article is accepted*).

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Author contributions

Juliette Cardoletti: contributed to the acquisition, analysis, interpretation of data and writing of the work. **Ivana Goričan and Matej Šadl:** contributed to the acquisition and analysis of data. **Hana Uršič:** contributed to the conception of the work and acquired the funding. **Sebastjan Glinšek:** contributed to the conception of the work and substantively revised it and acquired the funding.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Declaration of generative AI in scientific writing

The authors declare that they did not use generative AI to prepare this scientific article.

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